

Explicit High-Order ADE Solutions for Fluid Flow in the Coupled Biot Equations

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ABSTRACT

Explicit techniques have been used for simulating coupled fluid flow and geomechanical interactions in porous media. Still, the techniques are conditionally stable and require small time steps, affecting their efficiency for long-term simulations. To remove these restrictions, an unconditionally stable alternating direction explicit (ADE) scheme could be used to solve the flow problem. However, the standard ADE scheme is only moderately accurate and is restricted to uniform grids, thus impractical for large-scale domains. This paper introduces high-order ADE schemes capable of solving flow problems in non-uniform grids. The new schemes are derived from non-uniform fourth-order approximations to the spatial derivatives of the fluid-diffusion equations. The flow solutions are then sequentially coupled with a geomechanical simulator in the computer code Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua (FLAC). Validations on consolidation problems show that the new sequential coupling technique reduces simulation runtimes by 46-66% of FLAC's basic scheme without numerical instability and with maximum errors < 4%.

INTRODUCTION

Explicit coupling technique has been the most attractive approach to use for simulating the coupled fluid flow and geomechanical interactions in porous media. The explicit technique is not only simple to implement, but also less time consuming in building the separate fluid flow and geomechanical codes for solving the coupled Biot's equations (Biot 1941), while still able to capture the desired hydro-mechanical (H-M) interactions. Unfortunately, this holy grail of coupling techniques comes at a price: it is conditionally stable and requires small time steps to maintain numerical stability and accuracy. This strong limitation affects the efficiency of computer runtime for large-scale and long-term H-M simulations.

To remove the time step restriction, one proposed method is to use an unconditionally stable fluid flow scheme that can be sequentially coupled with an existing geomechanical simulator e.g., Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua or FLAC (Itasca 2011a). The alternating direction explicit (ADE) scheme is one such scheme. In an ADE scheme, two explicit finite difference (FD) equations are executed simultaneously in two physical directions: one in a forward sweep and the other in a reverse sweep (Figure 1). While both sweeps use the solutions from the previous time level (n), the forward sweep finds the solution to the target point at the next time level ($n + 1$) by

using the already calculated solutions at $(n + 1)$ located *behind* the target point (Figure 1a), whereas the reverse sweep uses those located *ahead* of the target point (Figure 1b).

Figure 1. Illustration of the standard ADE scheme (Prasetyo, 2017).

As an example, Barakat and Clark (1966) used an ADE scheme to solve the diffusion problem in Eq. (1) by executing two FD equations in the forward and reverse sweeps as shown in Eqs. (2) and (3), respectively.

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} \quad (1)$$

$$u_{i,j}^{n+1} = a u_{i,j}^n + b (u_{i-1,j}^{n+1} + u_{i+1,j}^n) + c (u_{i,j-1}^{n+1} + u_{i,j+1}^n) \quad (2)$$

$$v_{i,j}^{n+1} = a v_{i,j}^n + b (v_{i-1,j}^n + v_{i+1,j}^{n+1}) + c (v_{i,j-1}^n + v_{i,j+1}^{n+1}) \quad (3)$$

where a , b and c are the constants defined in Eq. (4). The final solution is the average of the solutions from the two sweeps as shown in Eq. (5).

$$a = \frac{1 - \Delta t (1/\Delta x^2 + 1/\Delta y^2)}{1 - \Delta t (1/\Delta x^2 + 1/\Delta y^2)} = \frac{1 - \lambda}{1 + \lambda}, \quad b = \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} \frac{1}{1 + \lambda}, \quad c = \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta y^2} \frac{1}{1 + \lambda} \quad (4)$$

$$p_{i,j}^{n+1} = \frac{1}{2} (u_{i,j}^{n+1} + v_{i,j}^{n+1}) \quad (5)$$

Despite its unconditional stability, the standard ADE scheme above has three major drawbacks. First, its low-order accuracy is challenged when a large time step size is desired for an efficient H-M simulation. Second, the limitation on uniform grid sizes makes it impractical for solving large-scale coupled problems that are usually arranged with gradually increasing grid size. Third, it cannot be used for solving axisymmetric fluid flow problems.

The goal of this paper is to eliminate the first two drawbacks by developing high-order ADE schemes for non-uniform grid. The third drawback is addressed in Prasetyo (2017). The pore pressure solutions from the new ADE scheme are then sequentially coupled with an explicit geomechanical simulator in FLAC, resulting in a novel and efficient sequential coupling technique.

DERIVATION OF HIGH-ORDER ADE SCHEMES

In this paper, the adopted sequential coupling technique freezes the mechanical deformation during fluid flow calculation ($\delta\varepsilon_{vol} = 0$). Hence, Biot's equation for fluid flow is only represented by a fluid-diffusion equation as shown in Eq. (6).

$$f = c_v \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $f = \partial p / \partial t$ and c_v is the coefficient of consolidation defined as $c_v = k M$, k is the mobility coefficient defined as $k = k_H / \gamma_w$, k_H is the hydraulic conductivity, γ_w is the unit weight of fluid and M is the Biot modulus.

To develop the proposed high-order ADE schemes for non-uniform grid, the second order derivatives in Eq. (6) must be approximated to the fourth-order accuracy. Consider a general non-uniform FD grid that consists of four quadrilateral elements as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Illustration of non-uniform FD grid.

Writing the Taylor series expansion for $p_{i+1,j}$ and $p_{i-1,j}$ to the fourth-order gives

$$p_{i+1,j} = p_{i,j} + \Delta x_+ \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta x_+^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} \right) + \frac{1}{6} \Delta x_+^3 \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial x^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} \Delta x_+^4 \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial x^4} \right) + O(\Delta x_+^4) \quad (7)$$

$$p_{i-1,j} = p_{i,j} - \Delta x_- \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta x_-^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} \right) - \frac{1}{6} \Delta x_-^3 \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial x^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} \Delta x_-^4 \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial x^4} \right) + O(\Delta x_-^4) \quad (8)$$

Multiplying $p_{i+1,j}$ by Δx_- and $p_{i-1,j}$ by Δx_+ and adding the results, and doing the same for $p_{i,j+1}$ and $p_{i,j-1}$ gives

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} = \delta_x^2 p_{i,j} - \frac{1}{12} \left[A \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial x^3} + B \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial x^4} \right] + O(\Delta x_-^4 + \Delta x_+^4) \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} = \delta_y^2 p_{i,j} - \frac{1}{12} \left[C \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial y^3} + D \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial y^4} \right] + O(\Delta y_-^4 + \Delta y_+^4) \quad (10)$$

Here, δ_x^2 and δ_y^2 are the centered difference operators for the second derivatives, defined as

$$\delta_x^2 p_{i,j} = \frac{2 \Delta x_+ p_{i-1,j} - 2(\Delta x_- + \Delta x_+) p_{i,j} + 2 \Delta x_- p_{i+1,j}}{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^2 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^2} \quad (11)$$

$$\delta_y^2 p_{i,j} = \frac{2 \Delta y_+ p_{i,j-1} - 2(\Delta y_- + \Delta y_+) p_{i,j} + 2 \Delta y_- p_{i,j+1}}{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^2 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^2} \quad (12)$$

The constants A , B , C and D are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A &= 4 \frac{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^3 - \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^3}{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^2 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^2}, & B &= \frac{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^4 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^4}{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^2 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^2} \\ C &= 4 \frac{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^3 - \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^3}{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^2 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^2}, & D &= \frac{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^4 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^4}{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^2 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^2} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

To have the fourth-order approximations for $\partial^2 p / \partial x^2$ and $\partial^2 p / \partial y^2$, the higher-order partial derivatives $\partial^3 p / \partial x^3$, $\partial^4 p / \partial x^4$, $\partial^3 p / \partial y^3$ and $\partial^4 p / \partial y^4$ in Eqs. (9) and (10) need to be further approximated to be second-order accurate. This operation gives

$$\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial x^3} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial x \partial y^2}, \quad \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial x^4} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial y^3} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial y \partial x^2}, \quad \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial y^4} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial y^2 \partial x^2} \quad (15)$$

Substituting these approximations in Eqs. (9) and (10) and adding the resulting equations gives the desired fourth-order compact scheme (after omitting the error terms) as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_x^2 p_{i,j} + \delta_y^2 p_{i,j} + \frac{1}{12} (A \delta_x \delta_y^2 + B \delta_x^2 \delta_y^2 + C \delta_y \delta_x^2 + D \delta_y^2 \delta_x^2) p_{i,j} \\ = \left[\frac{1}{c_v} + \frac{1}{12 c_v} (A \delta_x + B \delta_x^2 + C \delta_y + D \delta_y^2) \right] f_{i,j} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $f_{i,j}$, δ_x and δ_y are given as

$$f_{i,j} = \frac{P_{i,j}^{n+1} - P_{i,j}^n}{\Delta t}, \quad \delta_x p_{i,j} = \frac{P_{i+1,j} - P_{i-1,j}}{\Delta x_+ + \Delta x_-}, \quad \delta_y p_{i,j} = \frac{P_{i,j+1} - P_{i,j-1}}{\Delta y_+ + \Delta y_-} \quad (17)$$

The novel high-order ADE scheme for a non-uniform grid is obtained after applying the Crank-Nicolson (1947) technique to Eq. (16) and then arranging the resulting equation into the forward and reverse sweeps as previously shown in Eqs. (2) and (3). This operation gives

Forward sweep

$$u_{i,j}^{n+1} = \alpha_0 u_{i,j}^n + \alpha_1 u_{i-1,j}^{n+1} + \alpha_2 u_{i+1,j}^n + \alpha_3 u_{i,j-1}^{n+1} + \alpha_4 u_{i,j+1}^n + \alpha_5 u_{i-1,j-1}^{n+1} + \alpha_6 u_{i+1,j-1}^n + \alpha_7 u_{i-1,j+1}^{n+1} + \alpha_8 u_{i+1,j+1}^n + \beta_1 (u_{i-1,j}^{n+1} - u_{i-1,j}^n) + \beta_2 (u_{i,j-1}^{n+1} - u_{i,j-1}^n) \quad (18)$$

Reverse sweep

$$v_{i,j}^{n+1} = \alpha_0 v_{i,j}^n + \alpha_1 v_{i-1,j}^n + \alpha_2 v_{i+1,j}^{n+1} + \alpha_3 v_{i,j-1}^n + \alpha_4 v_{i,j+1}^{n+1} + \alpha_5 v_{i-1,j-1}^n + \alpha_6 v_{i+1,j-1}^{n+1} + \alpha_7 v_{i-1,j+1}^n + \alpha_8 v_{i+1,j+1}^{n+1} + \beta_3 (v_{i+1,j}^n - v_{i+1,j}^{n+1}) + \beta_4 (v_{i,j+1}^n - v_{i,j+1}^{n+1}) \quad (19)$$

where α_0 - α_8 and β_1 - β_4 are the grid size-dependent constants defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_0 &= \frac{\alpha_N}{\alpha_D} = \frac{1 - r \Delta t \left[\frac{1}{2}(a+b+c+d) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{12}(B+D)(a+b)(c+d) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{6}(B(a+b)+D(c+d)) \right]}{1 + r \Delta t \left[\frac{1}{2}(a+b+c+d) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{12}(B+D)(a+b)(c+d) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{6}(B(a+b)+D(c+d)) \right]} \\ \alpha_1 &= r \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} \left[a + \frac{1}{12}(Ah_x - a(B+D))(c+d) \right] & \alpha_2 &= r \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} \left[b - \frac{1}{12}(Ah_x + b(B+D))(c+d) \right] \\ \alpha_3 &= r \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} \left[c + \frac{1}{12}(Ch_y - c(B+D))(a+b) \right] & \alpha_4 &= r \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} \left[d - \frac{1}{12}(Ch_y + d(B+D))(a+b) \right] \\ \alpha_5 &= \frac{r}{12} \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} [ac(B+D) - aCh_y - cAh_x] & \alpha_6 &= \frac{r}{12} \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} [bc(B+D) - bCh_y + cAh_x] \\ \alpha_7 &= \frac{r}{12} \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} [ad(B+D) + aCh_y - dAh_x] & \alpha_8 &= \frac{r}{12} \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} [bd(B+D) + bCh_y + dAh_x] \\ \beta_1 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} [Ah_x - Bh_x] & \beta_2 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} [Ch_y - Dc] \\ \beta_3 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} [Ah_x + Bh_y] & \beta_4 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} [Ch_y + Dd] \\ a &= \frac{2\Delta x_+}{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^2 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^2} & b &= \frac{2\Delta x_-}{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^2 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^2} & h_x &= \frac{1}{\Delta x_+ + \Delta x_-} \\ c &= \frac{2\Delta y_+}{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^2 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^2} & d &= \frac{2\Delta y_-}{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^2 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^2} & h_y &= \frac{1}{\Delta y_+ + \Delta y_-} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Compared to the standard ADE scheme in Eqs. (2) and (3), the new ADE scheme has more points included in the calculation of the target point, e.g., more diagonal points from the cross-derivatives, due to the fourth-order approximation. The new high-order ADE scheme has been proven to be stable and consistent, guaranteeing the convergence of the solutions (Prasetyo 2017).

For solving coupled problems, the pore pressure solutions from the new ADE scheme are sequentially coupled with the geomechanical simulator in FLAC. This coupling technique in FLAC is called the sequentially-explicit coupling technique based on the fourth-order ADE scheme, abbreviated as SEA-4. The following sections present the results of validations of SEA-4 against well-known consolidations. The efficiency of SEA-4 is then compared to the fully-coupled approach in FLAC, which uses a conditionally stable basic flow scheme (Itasca 2011b).

VALIDATION AGAINST MANDEL'S CONSOLIDATION PROBLEM

SEA-4 is validated against Mandel's consolidation (Cheng and Detournay 1988). A rectangular soil sample is loaded by a vertical force $F = 100$ MN and is free to drain laterally. The FD grids are represented by quadrilateral elements, testing SEA-4 for an irregular domain. Due to the symmetry, only a quarter of the sample is modeled (Figure 3a). The material properties for Mandel and other consolidation problems in this paper are given in Table 1. The simulation is carried out for a total consolidation time of $t = 60$ h, corresponding to a normalized consolidation time of $t^* = 10$ ($t^* = c_v t/a^2$). The time step used in SEA-4 is $\Delta t = 2.4$ s, while that in FLAC's basic scheme is $\Delta t_{\text{cri}} = 0.7$ s (the critical value to maintain its stability). As shown in Figure 3b-d, the results from SEA-4 are nearly identical to the analytical results and to the numerical results from FLAC with error $< 3.4\%$ for pore pressure and 0.4% for displacement. Because a large time step is used, SEA-4 also reduces computer runtime by 66% compared to that of FLAC.

Table 1 Material properties for validations

Material properties	Mandel	Embankment
Hydraulic conductivity, k_H (m/s)	$9.6 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$5.8 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Porosity, ϕ	0.2	0.3
Shear modulus, G (Pa)	$2.5 \cdot 10^9$	$2.5 \cdot 10^6$
Drained bulk modulus, K (Pa)	$3.3 \cdot 10^9$	$5.4 \cdot 10^6$

Figure 3. Mandel's problem: (a) grid, (b) p/p_0 vs. t^* , (c) DOC vs. t^* and (d) p/p_0 vs. x/a .

VALIDATION AGAINST EMBANKMENT LOADING

SEA-4 is now validated against embankment loading on a saturated foundation. An elastic saturated foundation is loaded by an embankment of length $2a = 40$ m and a vertical load of $p_0 = 200$ kPa. The foundation is 40 m deep and 160 m wide. The domain is assumed to be initially stress-free, and due to the vertical symmetry, only half of the domain is modeled (Figure 4a). The

material properties are given in Table 1. The simulation is carried out for a total consolidation time of 100 years, which is 10 times the characteristic time of the problem ($t_c = H^2/c_v$). The time step used in SEA-4 is $\Delta t = 7.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ day, while that in FLAC's basic scheme is $\Delta t_{\text{cri}} = 2.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ day. Figure 4b shows the contour of pore pressure after a half-year. The comparison between SEA-4 and FLAC's basic scheme is very satisfactory. Further, at various consolidation times, the agreement on the settlement profile and pore pressure with depth between SEA-4 and FLAC is also excellent (Figure 4c and d, respectively). The settlement only induces average error of 1.5%, while the pore pressure induces error of 3.5%. Because a larger time step size is used in SEA-4, the computer runtime is reduced by 46%, from 47 minutes in FLAC to only 25 minutes in SEA-4.

Figure 4. Embankment loading: (a) grid, (b) pore pressure contour (c) Settlement and (d) pore pressure with depth.

CONCLUSIONS

This study developed unconditionally stable high-order ADE schemes for a non-uniform grid capable of solving flow problems in plane strain conditions. The resulting pore pressure solutions from the new ADE scheme were sequentially coupled with the geomechanical simulator

in FLAC. This coupling technique is called the sequentially-explicit coupling technique based on the fourth-order ADE scheme, abbreviated as SEA-4.

Validations against Mandel's consolidation and embankment loading showed that SEA-4 reduced computer runtimes by 46-66% compared to FLAC's basic scheme without numerical instability and only induced maximum errors of less than 4% for both pore pressure and displacement solutions. Thus, the results in this paper suggest that the newly derived high-order ADE schemes will open up avenues for accurate and efficient H-M simulations involving coupled Biot's equations. This may include the potential of the new scheme to be coupled with other existing geomechanical simulators, widening its future application for solving larger geoen지니어ing problems involving coupled fluid flow and geomechanical interactions in porous media.

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